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THE IMPORTANCE OF MATHEMATICAL STATISTICS IN MEDICINE

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Annotation: *Mathematical statistics is widely used in medicine as an essential tool for forecasting diseases, evaluating the effectiveness of treatments, and improving the efficiency of healthcare systems. Through statistical methods, the dynamics of disease spread, clinical trials, genetic research, and the effectiveness of healthcare systems are analyzed. This article discusses the role of mathematical statistics in medicine, including disease forecasting, clinical trials, and personalized treatment.*

Keywords: *mathematical statistics, medicine, clinical trials, disease forecasting, epidemiology, healthcare systems.*

Introduction. Mathematical statistics is a fundamental tool for scientific research in medicine. With the help of medical statistical methods, the spread of diseases can be analyzed, new treatments can be tested, and the effectiveness of healthcare systems can be assessed. Statistical analysis plays a significant role in identifying patients, preventing diseases, and improving the effectiveness of treatments. Furthermore, statistics is also used in developing personalized treatment approaches and in genomic analysis.

Studying the Spread of Diseases. Epidemiological studies are a major field of application for mathematical statistics in analyzing the spread of diseases. Statistical analyses, such as regression analysis and multivariate modeling, are used to identify disease spread and risk factors. For example, the spread of cardiovascular diseases or oncological diseases can be forecasted and public health improvement strategies can be developed. During the COVID-19 pandemic, statistical models were employed to analyze disease spread, high-risk groups, and coverage rates. A study by Flaxman et al. (2020) used mathematical models to assess various scenarios of the pandemic’s spread, leading to the implementation of strict measures worldwide. Statistics can be

used to predict the spread of diseases and develop effective measures to prevent pandemics.

Clinical Trials and Statistics Clinical trials are crucial in determining the effectiveness and safety of new treatments in medicine. Clinical trials, particularly randomized controlled trials (RCTs), are widely used to assess the efficacy of treatments. Statistical methods are applied to analyze the results of these trials, compare patient groups, and measure the safety and effectiveness of treatments. For example, a study by Dixon et al. (2017) used statistical methods to analyze the efficacy of statin therapy in cardiovascular diseases. Through statistical methods, error rates, p-values, and risk assessments of clinical trials are evaluated.

The results of clinical trials are typically based on medical statistical models, such as the Cox regression model or Kaplan-Meier analysis, which provide the most accurate and reliable results in evaluating new treatments. Additionally, statistical methods allow for the creation of personalized approaches by considering the individual characteristics of patients, the stages of diseases, and the treatment methods applied.

Genomics and Personalized Medicine In the field of genomics, mathematical statistics plays a crucial role, especially in analyzing genomic data. In personalized medicine, statistics are used to develop treatment plans tailored to individual patients. For example, in cancer treatment, genetic markers are used to analyze a patient's unique genetic characteristics and develop treatment strategies based on that analysis. A study by Esteva et al. (2019) demonstrated the successful application of machine learning algorithms and statistical models in the early detection of dermatological diseases, particularly skin cancer. Statistical analysis aids in the study of genomic data and is also useful in identifying genetic factors contributing to diseases.

Through genomics and bioinformatics, statistical methods are employed in genomic research, such as integrating genetic variants, mutations, and data. These methods help study the genetic factors of diseases and develop treatment approaches based on new biomarkers.

Healthcare Systems and Statistics In improving the efficiency of healthcare systems, statistical methods can be applied to analyze the functioning of healthcare systems, allocate resources effectively, and predict the number of patients. A study by Porter and Kaplan (2014) emphasized the importance of using statistical analysis methods to improve the efficiency of medical services. In healthcare systems, statistical models are vital for analyzing costs and optimizing resource allocation.

Through statistical analysis, it is possible to predict the effectiveness of healthcare systems, improve patient admission processes, and enhance treatment outcomes. Additionally, statistical models are used to optimize resource allocation in healthcare settings, such as managing patient flow in hospitals and clinics.

Conclusion: Mathematical statistics is an indispensable tool in scientific research and clinical practice in medicine. Through statistical methods, it is possible to analyze disease spread, evaluate clinical trial results, study genetic data, and improve the efficiency of healthcare systems. Moreover, statistics creates opportunities for integrating new technologies, such as artificial intelligence and genomics, in medicine. However, to effectively utilize these technologies, it is crucial to ensure data security and further deepen statistical analysis.

References:

1. **Dixon, S., et al.** (2017). *The Role of Statin Therapy in Cardiovascular Disease: A Statistical Analysis of Clinical Trials.* *Lancet*, 389(10064), 1139-1147.
2. **Esteva, A., et al.** (2019). *A Guide to Artificial Intelligence in Biomedicine.* MIT Press.
3. **Flaxman, S., et al.** (2020). Estimates of the Effects of Non-Pharmaceutical Interventions on COVID-19 in Europe. *Nature*, 584(7820), 257-261.
4. **Jha, S.** (2021). *AI in Genomics and Personalized Medicine.* *Nature Medicine*, 27(3), 338.
5. Abdullayeva B., Aliyev N. Pedagogical Ability In Self-Development Of A Future Primary School Teacher //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 149-153.
6. Aliyev N., Ergasheva D. METHODS OF PROFESSIONAL SELF-DEVELOPMENT OF A PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHER //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. B8. – С. 1679-1681.
7. Aliyev N., Muhammadjonov S. THE ROLE OF MATHEMATICS EDUCATION IN THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF MEDICAL WORKERS. THE IMPORTANCE OF MATHEMATICS FOR A HEALTH WORKER. MATHEMATICAL METHODS AND STATISTICS IN MEDICINE //Бюллетень педагогов нового Узбекистана. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 39-42.
8. 4. Nurillo N. A., Muhammadjonov S., Tojimatova L. THE ROLE OF MATHEMATICS EDUCATION IN THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF MEDICAL PERSONNEL. THE IMPORTANCE OF MATHEMATICS FOR THE HEALTH WORKER //International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 54-56.
9. Abdullayeva B., Aliyev N. Bo‘lajak boshlang‘ich sinf o‘qituvchisining o‘z-o‘zini rivojlantirishda pedagogik qobiliyatning ahamiyati //Бюллетень педагогов нового Узбекистана. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 74-78.

10. Abdiqayumovich A. N., Abdiqayumovna I. M. Fur'e Method for Solving Boundary Value Problems Placed in Parabolic Type Equations //Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 11. – C. 107-113.
11. Abdullayeva B. S., Aliyev N. A., qizi Ergasheva D. S. Improving self-development competency of future primary class teachers //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 7. – C. 274-277.
12. Sayfutdinova A. B., Abdiqayumovich A. N. THEORETICAL ISSUES OF INCREASING TEACHING EFFICIENCY BASED ON MODERN ADVANCED PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PRIMARY CLASS //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 10. – №. 11. – C. 233-239.
13. Abdullayeva Barno Sayfutdinovna, & Aliyev Nurillo Abdiqayumovich. (2022). IMPROVING THE COMPETENCE OF THE FUTURE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHER IN SELF-DEVELOPMENT. European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements, 3(12), 12-14.
14. Abdikayumovich A. N. et al. Innovative Approaches in Mathematics (Pisa and Timss Programs) //American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research. – 2021. – T. 2. – №. 9. – C. 116-118.
15. Yusupova A. K., Aliyev N. A. SOME CONSIDERATIONS FOR TEACHING PROBABILITY THEORY AND MATHEMATICAL STATISTICS //Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 11. – C. 1183-1191.
16. AB Sayfutdinovna, AN Abdiqayumovich IMPROVING SELF-DEVELOPMENT COMPETENCY OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS // Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal 3 (8), 509-512.
17. Abdullayeva, B. S., Abdullayeva, B. S., & Aliyev, N. A. (2023). BO'LAJAK BOSHLANG'ICH SINFI O'QITUVCHILARINI O'Z-O'ZINI RIVOJLANTIRISH KO'NIKMALARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(13), 605–609.
18. Aliyev, N; Davronova, N. (2023). PULMONOLOGIYA TARIXI VA HOZIRGI KUNDAGI AHAMIYATI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(13), 610-613.
19. N.A.Aliyev. (2023). FORMATION OF SELF-DEVELOPMENT SKILLS FOR FUTURE PRIMARY TEACHERS. Scientific Impulse, 2(15), 363–367

20. Aliyev, N. A., & Sobirova, M. R. qizi. (2023). MASALALAR BILAN DASTLABKI TANISHUVNING INNOVATSION ASOSLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(16), 659–666.
21. Melibayeva, F. M., Aliyev, N. A., & Muhammadjonov, S. G. o'g'li. (2023). CHEKISH BILAN BOG'LIQ O'PKA KASALIKLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(16), 719–723.
- 22.18. Melibayeva, F. M., Aliyev, N. A., & Muhammadjonov, S. G. o'g'li. (2023). KOMPYUTER TEXNOLOGIYALARI ORQALI KELIB CHIQUADIGAN KASALLIKLARNI OLDINI OLISH. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(16), 705-708.
23. AN Abdiqayumovich, M Sarvarbek Gayratjon o'g'li. ZAMONAVIY DIAGNOSTIKANING ROLI. ZAMONAVIY DIAGNOSTIKA USULLARI. Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования 10 (6), 177-180.
24. Abdiqayumovich A. N. TEJAMKORLIKKA OID MASALALAR ISHLASHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUV //STUDIES IN ECONOMICS AND EDUCATION IN THE MODERN WORLD. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 1. – C. 64-71.
25. Abdiqayumovich A. N. TIBBBIY BILIMLARNI O'RGATISHDA MASOFAVIY TA'LIM TIZIMINI TADBIQ ETISH //TADQIQOTLAR. UZ. – 2024. – T. 36. – №. 3. – C. 104-111.